

**DECOLONIAL BIBLICAL COMMENTARY: PAUL, FRONTIER
THEOLOGY AND BRAZILIAN COLONIALITY⁴** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8432206**Eduardo Sales de Lima**

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ABSTRACT

We are currently witnessing the organization of postcolonial ideals in different epistemological perspectives. Coloniality, the main problem, is a reality that affects both the colonized and the colonizers. Classical reading and interpretation mechanisms were, and still are, hostages to the epistemes of colonial domination. And, alongside these documents, biblical reading plays an active role in colonial and decolonial relations. Theologians, mainly from Africa and India, have identified the Bible as an instrument of colonial domination. In view of this, our objective is to propose a biblical reinterpretation based on Paul and his writings, observing the post-colonial proposal, articulating concepts from Darcy Ribeiro and Glória Anzáldua. To do this, we will situate the elements of post-colonial thinking and the forms of comparison and identification for this reinterpretation. Next, we will take a look at the texts that relate to Paulo's biography, seeking to understand the possibility of a frontier mentality. This proposal is justified due to the need for a critical look that integrates elements of the post-colonial episteme with the classical interpretation. It is also justified due to the role of religion in the configuration of society and its relationships. It is expected to identify possible decolonial relationships in Paul's actions and writings, identifying him as a frontier theologian. As a methodology, a comparative analysis will be carried out based on Paulo's biographies, relating the data to post-colonial narratives. It will be a reading based on applied and exploratory bibliographical research. Data processing will be qualitative.

Keywords : Post-colonial; Paul; Border.

INTRODUCTION

As research on coloniality develops, it becomes necessary to better understand the meaning of this relationship between colonized and colonizer. This is because the work and research has been developed based on foreign reflections and parameters based on studies from

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other colonial realities. But is this really possible? Could it be that the change in historical context and the differences in the formation of subjectivities do not influence the final meaning of what coloniality would be?

Faced with these initial questions, this work proposes a look at the formative context of the concept of coloniality, consulting traditional bibliographic references as well as reflecting on their validity for the formation of the concept.

These provocations also lead us to think about Brazilian coloniality. Does something like that exist? Is this practice of thinking based on universal concepts sufficient to deal with coloniality in Brazil? Currently, it seems that research practically does not use texts by Brazilians. Even when writing about coloniality, foreign literature is used. Therefore, a review of this paradigm is necessary. It is necessary to question Eurocentrism in Brazilian research and academic training.

And how does this relationship between the concept of coloniality and the Brazilian perspective help in identifying Paulo as a border theologian?

Traditionally, coloniality is studied in classical perceptions, but there are other possibilities. The proposals of border studies represent another possible reading to deal with coloniality. Thus, this work aims to understand the concept of border mentality and the possible relationships between the concept and the practice of the apostle Paul recorded in the Bible.

To achieve this, the research will use the Bible as a textual source about the Pauline experience. It will also use partial bibliographical research to conceptualize coloniality and its impact on the Brazilian scenario.

Finally, it is hoped that this work will broaden the understanding of the meaning of coloniality, position current theories and present the place of border mentality to compare with practices of Paul's ministry. If our hypothesis is validated, this re-reading of Paul from a frontier mentality allows new perspectives of reading and meaning for the reading of the Bible and for national theological reflection.

1. Problem and Problematics: Colonialities and Decolonialities

The topic is recent for Brazilian research. In the *Capes Periodicals* database, for example, in a search for subjects using the following key: *decolonial* or *coloniality* or *post-colonial*, in the period from 2000 to 2010 we found 171 results; from 2010 to 2015 there are 426 results; from 2015 to 2020, there are 1468 results; and from January 2020 to January 2022

there are more than 950 occurrences. This highlights a growing emphasis on the study of this topic in Brazilian territory.

Known as studies on coloniality, these are academic and literary research and productions generally identified with relationships after the *end of major colonizations*. According to Luciana Ballestrin's *Giro Decolonial* (2013, p. 92-93), it can be identified that there is a kind of “classic content” (which the author herself recognizes as subject to questioning) with seminal references to the texts of Franz Fanon (1925 -1961), Aimé Césaire (1913-2008) and Albert Memmi (1920-2020). Then, with texts by Edward Saïd (1935-2003), Gayatri C. Spivak (1942-) and Homi K. Bhabha (1949-). For Ballestrin, the beginning of these studies is classified into groups: the French Triad and its developments; the Subaltern Studies Group, in the 1970s, with a greater representation of thinkers from India; the Modernity and Coloniality Group in the United States and the Latin American Subaltern Studies Group and the South Asian Subaltern Studies Group, all from the 1990s onwards.

But care must be taken with this definition. Studies on coloniality are not a school or philosophical line, nor a line of thought or an academic theory, they are not ideals with absolutist and universal pretensions. This can be confirmed in the writers of post-colonialism. The video released on the TED channel, “The danger of a unique story” by Chimamanda Adichie, helps with this understanding by identifying coloniality through the relationship between particular and universal. Chimamanda's reflection highlights the fact, the historicity that imposes itself in the face of universal narratives, thus, when reading the various works that deal with coloniality it is possible to deduce its origin as a denunciation from situations of local suffering during and after the departure of the colonizers. And decolonial theories are based on continuities and ruptures with colonial differences. Reports and reflections that extend decolonial knowledge to other places and times, not limited to academic discourse. The texts by Peruvian chronicler Felipe Guaman Poma de Ayala, in the book “*Nueva Corónica y Buen Gobierno*” (1615) and the Brazilian magazine *Antropofagia* from 1929, are examples of critical reflection against the continuity of colonial violence, therefore, decolonial. This is no different in the narratives of the Judeo-Christian Bible, our object of study, which relates contexts of colonial domination (Egyptian, Assyrian, Babylonian, Persian, Greek, Maccabean, Roman).

Therefore, as an initial conceptualization, coloniality, a term coined by Anibal Quijano (2007), can be understood as the result/difference during and after the physical *departure of the colonizers*. It is all the influence and cultural residue that acts on the colonies and the colonizers in order to continue the relationship of domination through the epistemic control of the

subjectivities of both cultures. It is not a thought or ideology, but a denunciation of the continuity of violence under colonial domination.

Faced with this reality, postcolonial studies emerged that assumed decolonial/decolonial positions in search of freedom and epistemic autonomy. In general, two main paths developed: one of aversion, repulsion and distancing from colonial logics; and another, hybridist, focused on accepting new realities that emerged through the colonial relationship. These are not exclusive paths, but complementary. Both are characterized as post-colonial and decolonial and have in common the need to question colonial difference/result. They do not accept the continuity of epistemologies of domination and propose another possible reality, dialoguing in post-critical perspectives with hegemonic cultures.

With this we have three considerations. The first concerns the identification of coloniality. As a complaint, it is not limited to a beginning, a line of thought, a type, or a school, but exists in any reality where there is a colonial relationship. The second indicates that studies on coloniality unfolded into decolonial stances. They can be about preserving national identity in the face of cultural invasion and domination; and hybridism, focused on valuing the new dispositions that resulted from the cultural encounter (RUKUNDWA, 2008). And the third is about the non-pretension of universality. This is because universality is a colonial and dominating reference. The moment a decolonial proposal reduces history to universal values, it becomes another form of epistemic domination.

As a complaint, there is no pattern on how coloniality manifests itself. There are some impressions that are repeated, such as the ideas of superiority and inferiority that manifest themselves in all cultures, impacting both subjectivities. Racism and ethnocentrism are also perceived as consequences of absolutist and classificatory logics legitimizing their control and cultural dominance. Quijano, and later post-colonialist writers, agreed to think about the effects of coloniality in terms of Coloniality of Power, Coloniality of Being and Coloniality of Knowledge (BALESTRIN, 2013). However, it is necessary to remember that there is no absolute standard, as every causal relationship must be mediated by subjectivity. Thus, coloniality depends on the marks left and felt, which is why it is different in different places and can be different for different people, even in the same context.

1.1 Problems in Brazil: Epistemological domination and hybridism

In post-colonial biblical readings practiced by African and Indian theologians, for example, the decolonial stance of defending and valuing local culture predominates, with some

hybridist readings (RUKUNDWA, 2008). It is not the application of a methodology, but rather reflections based on popular and academic complaints. Of these works, the writings of Musa W. Dube and Rasiah S. Sugirtharajah stand out, who, like several others, develop post-colonial biblical readings based on criticisms of imperialism. This proposal confronts the biased relationship between biblical interpretations, questions the colonial epistemological paradigm that decides interpretation and presents readings of coloniality in biblical narratives in relation to current coloniality. Thus, it emphasizes national characteristics and values local culture in the face of foreign domination.

However, in the Brazilian context this was not quite the case. European colonization had a greater cultural impact on Brazil than on neighboring countries such as Colombia, Peru, Bolivia, Ecuador, countries that continue to value native cultural elements. In Brazil, coloniality developed several practices to purge the native cultural component, particularly policies aimed at whitening the people (DÁVILA, 2005). These *eugenic policies* generated profound changes in the episteme, including the formation of various prejudices, mainly in relation to *indigenous and black people* (emphasizing the third person) considered backward or impure. A kind of semi-European/North American identity was created, whose traits mainly influence elites and academic-cultural leaders, and, from there, reach the entire society.

Brazilian coloniality developed much more in hybridism than in cultural resistance. This can be seen by the emphasis on diversity and interaction in different areas, from language to food, from fashion to musical and artistic culture in general. And, even among religious groups considered radical, diversity and plurality can be seen. Which is not necessarily good, as both hybridity and cultural resistance follow the colonial episteme when they absolutize their discourse, either by opposing cultural invasion or by lack of resistance to hybridity, only assuming the identity of the other. Thus, in academic productions, for example, there is a strong Eurocentric influence, justifying the *semi-European civilized* identity project .

To understand a little better, the hybridist reason Homi Bhabha's studies have stood out, especially with the book "The place of Culture". In it, the author presents the hybrid as a space of encounter and difference, something rich and a carrier of cultural development (BHABHA, 2001). This hybridism is also an old acquaintance of anthropological and linguistic studies (HANNERS, 1997). However, it is among Brazilian writers that we get an explanation that is closer to our reality.

Among these, Gilberto Freyre in "Casa Grande e Senzala" written in 1933 describing Brazil through the intersection of Portuguese, Amerindians and Africans; this for a more technical and academic reading (FREYRE, 2001). But also the works of Jorge Amado, in the

novels “Dona Flor and her two husbands” (1966) and “Tenda dos Milagres” (1969), examples of texts with different realistic readings about the national condition and cultural hybridisms. I also highlight the works of anthropologist Darcy Ribeiro who, due to his work among indigenous tribes, realized the need for cultural resistance in the face of foreign logic of domination. An example can be read in the narratives about the Indian Isaías (RIBEIRO, 1977). Brazilian coloniality can be identified in the publications of Darcy Ribeiro, “The Brazilian indigenous policy” (1962), “Historical-cultural configurations of the American peoples” (1975); “The civilizing process – stages of socio-cultural evolution” (1968); “The Latin American dilemma: power structures and insurgent forces” (1978); “The Brazilians: Theory of Brazil” (1972); and several other writings neglected by Eurocentric practices. There are still several writers in Brazil who present and question post-colonial phenomena. In academia, for example, we have the writings of Guerreiro Ramos and Milton Santos, and in literature, the example of the magazine *Antropofagia* (1928-1929) created by Oswald de Andrade and Raul Bopp; in texts and stories such as “O Espelho” (1882) by Machado de Assis, and many others. This can also be seen in films, the acclaimed “Que hora ela volta” written and directed by Anna Muylaert, is an example.

Recently, due to the greater representation of decolonial studies, more texts and research on cultural and epistemic resistance have emerged, valuing and preserving the singularities of feminist movements, blackness, diversity and gender, indigenous movements and others. Reflections on coloniality are also present in several areas of knowledge, moving national reflection towards what Guerreiro Ramos (1969, p.48) called national critical consciousness.

Given this situation, we understand that the reading and reflection on the Bible practiced in Brazil is closer to hybrid formulations than to cultural resistance. And even with the social changes of the last 50 years, in which biblical reading came closer to movements fighting for land and the cry for social justice (liberation theology), the episteme continued to be subjugated to the Eurocentric proposal, weakening national identity. And, this hybrid, *semi-European identity*, which renounced cultural resistance, became hostage to neoliberal projects, accepting the continuity of colonial exploitation via cultural domination. This *hybrid national project* is validated by scientific and religious epistememes by accepting the reduction of life to economic results. The development of the hybridist episteme under the tutelage of the neoliberal project perpetuates the weakening of local culture in the face of the promotion of cultures of domination, causing decolonial denunciations of violence, exploitation, racism and usurpation to be naturalized as inevitable contemporary situations.

2. Border Thinking: A third way in decolonial perception.

Although little developed, there is still a third way of interpreting the problem of coloniality: border thinking. Unlike the proposals above, border thinking maintains tension and ambiguity. While opening up to cultural hybridity, it also affirms local identity and culture. Among the postcolonial thinkers from this perspective, we have Glória Evangelina Anzaldúa and Walter Mignolo.

In anthropological studies there are also fundamental readings on border thinking. According to Hannerz (1997), the border can be understood as a form of social organization through the relationship of belonging and control of cultural goods. This perception contributes to the understanding of “*mestizo*” by Eric Wolf (1959, p.238-241), an identity that breaks with the paradigms of cultural magnitudes and proposes the ability to move between cultures, to adapt to different situations, with great fluidity between different social mechanisms. Glória Anzaldúa also proposes a reflection on *mestizo* identity based on the Mexican philosopher José Vasconcelos, understanding that border thinking can be understood as a new consciousness (ANZALDUA, 2005). She proposes the experience of Chicano culture, in the inner (epistemic) clash between cultural ambiguities.

The new *mestiza* faces all this by developing a tolerance for contradictions, a tolerance for ambiguities. She learns to be an Indian in Mexican culture, to be Mexican from an Anglo-American point of view. Learn to balance cultures. It has a plural personality, it operates in a pluralistic mode – nothing is set aside, the good, the bad, the ugly, nothing is rejected, nothing abandoned. It not only sustains contradictions but also transforms ambivalence into something else. (ANZALDUA, 2005, p.706)

With the colonial project comes the challenge of living in the midst of diversities and differences, and Anzaldúa's *mestiza consciousness* is a response to balancing cultures, valuing others while recognizing the value of local culture, without eliminating ambiguity and contradictions, but circulating between them.

Thus, the border mentality should not be confused with hybridity. This is because cultural ambiguities and differences are maintained at the border and greater interactions are established, some hybrid and others of cultural resistance. When we compare the narratives about *mestiza* in the Chicano reality, with Brazilian hybridism, we identify that the border mentality forms an identity capable of moving between different cultures, which, in the Chicano case, adapts to white North American culture without leaving the culture Mexican. In Brazilian hybridity, on the other hand, there is nothing to return to, only the new reality established

through adaptation to the new culture. However, in border regions it is possible to identify this transcultural mentality.

2.1 Paul, a frontier theologian

Traditionally, biographies of Paul identified him as a theologian, thinker, pastor and missionary. However, I propose to observe Paul's actions from a mixed-race consciousness, as a frontier theologian. For this verification, we will use the texts preserved in biblical literature as a documentary source for comparison between Paulo's experience and the post/de-colonial texts of Darcy Ribeiro and Glória Anzaldúa.

Pax - Roman control parameters (WENGST, 1991) . In it it is possible to identify passages of resistance, hybridisms, various ambiguities and, added to the colonial legacies experienced by the people of Israel, a biased and ambiguous knowledge is formed. For example, in the Bible, one can notice aversion to Babylon and its form of oppressive politics, however, several elements of Babylonian language and culture were assimilated, mainly in ritual forms and in the understanding of the sacred (LIMA, 2013). And, despite feeling hatred due to colonial suffering and exploitation, many Jews preferred not to return to Jerusalem, as the tradition of the book of Esther testifies. This ambiguous relationship is presented by Darcy Ribeiro as something confusing, a mix of aversion and desire, the desire to be someone like the colonizer without devaluing one's own uniqueness, the need to “accept myself as I am, to more respect his work in myself [of God]” (RIBEIRO, 1977, p.20).

Given this context, Paul's decolonial endeavor began in Judaism. He left his cultural context (Greek) to study in Jerusalem, at the feet of Gamaliel (Acts 22:3). First, he had to learn to be a Greek in Jewish culture. The biblical text even presents Paul's role in visiting synagogues to defend Jewish culture (Gal 1:13-14; Phil 3:4-6; 1 Tim 1:13; and also in Acts 8:1,3; 9:1-4, 21).

And, due to his experience with Christ, Paul needed to learn to be a Jewish-Christian in Greek and Roman cultures, including local particularities. Thus, the narratives were reversed and the texts presented Paul facing the Gentiles/Greeks. It migrates/flows from a decolonial stance of cultural defense and ethnic-religious purism to a stance of inclusion and acceptance of diversity. This demonstrates that his theology was disobeying the dominant epistemes. One of the results is the re-reading of the Jewish faith from a Christian perspective (the re-reading of the traditions of Abraham in Rom 4, for example). Like *the mestiza* , he “Reinterprets history and, using new symbols, gives form to new myths” (ANZALDUA, 2005, p. 709). Thus, Paul

recognizes other cultures as participants in a sacred that was previously exclusive to the Jews (Gal 2-5; Rm 1:16; 2:29; 3-8; 9-11; specifically Gl 3:28; Col 3:11) , and all this without diluting and devaluing Jewish culture itself (1Co 7:18-24; Rom 9-11).

Paul develops the border mentality by proposing a gospel as a cross-cultural proclamation. It was an inclusive message, good news that broke with exclusionary paradigms, and without diluting the local culture, because while it includes, it does not reject cultures, it even maintains differences (1Co 7:18-24; Rom 14) . Thanks to this fluidity, Paulo conceived of the person as independent of the social paradigms of the time. In this way, he confronted racism, machismo and the relations of slavery resulting from coloniality with the proclamation of the gospel. Paul understood the gospel as a form of liberation, so he made it possible for other people to also live under this border paradigm, free from cultural domination (1Co 9:19-23; Gal 3:28; Col 3:11).

In the conflict narrated in Acts 15 and Galatians 2, known as the first church council, it is possible to understand the role of the border in control over cultural goods (HANNERS, 1997). The Judeo-Christian community at the time exercised control over religion and the sacred as a cultural asset, regulating access to the sacred. Therefore, Paul's attitude in including the Gentiles in the covenant without the obligation to comply with the law of Moses and Jewish traditions was not an affront to Jewish culture. Paul was not denying traditions, but recognizing the value of other cultures and confronting forms of cultural domination. With this he identified a space where the sacred was possible for people who were not committed to Jewish culture. Thus, he develops border thinking, which he himself defines in several texts (e.g. 1Co 9:19-23; Phil 3:3-9; Gal 1-2; Eph 2). This proposal allows us to reinterpret the understanding of the Pauline episteme and understand that faith is not a crystallized position, but a form of plural access to a place of hope and freedom (Col 1:13).

After his experience with the Son of God, Paul assumes a different place, and renounces cultural rigidity, perceiving Christ as a proposal for inclusion and overcoming paradigms inherited from colonial domination. According to Paul, Christ was the new in-between place where the saint and the sinner coexisted, where dualities and classifications were dissolved without dissolving cultural individualities (Rom 1:16; Gal 3:28; Col 3:11; 1Co 7:18-24 ; Rom 14). Paulo, like *the mestiza* , developed an identity capable of

move out of crystallized formations – of habit; away from convergent thinking, from analytical reasoning that tends to use rationality towards a single objective (a Western way), to divergent thinking, characterized by a movement away from established standards and objectives, towards a more broad, which includes rather than excludes. (ANZÁLDUA, 2005. p. 706).

Paulo, as a frontier theologian, develops an epistemology tolerant of contradictions and ambiguities, capable of balancing cultures by developing a “plural personality” (ANZALDUA 2005, p.706). In his writings Paul does not dissolve contradictions. Thus, he becomes a transcultural citizen who circulates in different cultures, without diluting or eliminating the different ones, on the contrary, respecting local cultures and at the same time inhabiting a space not controlled by classificatory ideologies, this in-between place is the place of culture, a fertile space for the birth of Christianity.

Conclusion

Currently, post/de-colonial studies on Brazilian soil have multiplied. This makes it possible to identify forms of ideological crystallization and categorical formations intending to limit the meaning of coloniality to a line of research in a given period, which clearly does not account for reality. This is because empires and their colonies have existed for millennia, as have post-colonial conditions. Forms of cultural domination can be studied in the first empires through the imposition of cultural logics that shaped the episteme. Therefore, a broader understanding of the meaning of coloniality is necessary that can account for the different contexts, times and impacts on the subjectivities of both colonizers and colonized people.

A broad proposal is important to understand the Brazilian scenario. Thus, the understanding of our coloniality must not be based on foreign literature, but on the histories and traditions that preserved and preserve the denunciations of our people in the face of the continuity of forms of domination. This becomes clear when we compare Brazilian cultural resistance literature with the cultural resistance literature of other colonized peoples, identifying the presence of cultural hybridity as one of the main hallmarks of Brazilian coloniality.

These two reading keys are fundamental to understanding Paul’s role as a frontier theologian. Thus, we understand that Paulo worked in a period and region with multiple experiences related to colonization. In his work he sought to balance cultures and developed the ability to adapt to cultural differences. He learned to move between cultures without disregarding the values of other peoples or even the traditions in which he was formed. He began his experience from a cultural defense perspective, but later, due to his mission, he developed the ability to tolerate differences, and circulate/flow between cultures. Postures that postcolonial research has defined as border mentality/thinking.

But what does this represent for post/de-colonial research in Brazil?

It helps in understanding that cultural hybridity can be harmful and serve universalistic patterns of cultural domination. This occurs when subjectivities are diluted in diversity, losing identity characteristics, creating workers for free trade without cultural ties. Subjectivities ready to adapt to satisfy the interests of society.

And, although the biblical text was used as a colonial ideological tool in shaping the subalternized imaginary, it is necessary to understand that Paul does not see the gospel like that. For this theologian, the gospel was a message of rupture, a border mentality that enabled people to take a critical look at the logics of cultural domination, even allowing the necessary fluidity for multicultural contexts.

The border proposal is not an understanding of Brazilian soil, even though Darcy Ribeiro's texts sometimes emphasize this double aspect without reducing the ambiguities. But it is possible to establish a double dialogue. First, with the re-reading of the biblical text itself, by identifying and valuing cultural parameters; by denouncing the narratives used for cultural domination, confronting them with narratives of resistance, hybridism and, mainly, with border proposals allowing new paths for cultural relations in Brazilian territory.

This re-reading of Paul also allows for several theological resignifications. This is because what really is Pauline thought and practice must be identified and separated from what theology dominated by colonial paradigms has identified as Pauline theology and thought.

Thus, it is concluded that, based on Paul's experience, it is possible to present a reading of the Bible that values different cultures without diluting one's own identity and without eliminating different cultures and understandings of the sacred. Frontier thinking is a perspective where ambiguity remains. And, precisely because it is a space where differences can coexist without the need for synthesis, it becomes an opportunity to critically think about reality.

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